

HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AND SELF-EFFICACY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATORS AS PREDICTORS OF STUDENTS' WELL-BEING

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Healthy Lifestyle and Self-Efficacy of Physical Educators as Predictors of Students' Well-being

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Abstract

The health challenges confronted by the college students resulted in considerable repercussions for their overall well-being. The school of physical education has always encouraged healthy activities guided with the idea that health comes first. This quantitative study aimed to determine the degree of influence of healthy lifestyle and physical educators' self-efficacy in students' well-being among college students. The regression analysis technique was used to determine the degree of relationship between the two independent variables and one independent variable. The researchers employed cluster sampling technique in selecting the right sample. After the thorough examination and the null hypothesis was assessed at 0.05 level of significance. This study delineated that healthy lifestyle do not influence students' well-being with the r-value of 0.019 and p-value of 0.056. Moreover, physical educators' self-efficacy positively influences students' well-being with the r-value of 0.196 and p-value of 0.001. The study accentuated that despite healthy lifestyle among college students do not influence students' well-being and physical educators' self-efficacy only correlates with students' well-being but, it is still vital and crucial in sustaining and maintaining the overall well-being of college students which is considered one of important keys in academic success in higher education institutions.

Keywords: *students' healthy lifestyle, self-efficacy of physical educators, students' well-being, quantitative design, physical education, Philippines*

Introduction

Schools are on the rise. Physical education is critical for a student's overall moral, intellectual, and physical development. School physical education has always encouraged healthy activity, guided by the idea that "health comes first" (An et al., 2022). Equally, when it comes to health, the establishment of a mindful attitude is of the utmost importance, and students are more likely to take part in physical exercise when exposed to contemporary methodologies and health initiatives (Olexandra et al., 2023). Therefore, it is essential that considering the causes of a sedentary lifestyle, students must engage in healthy activity to instill in them the desire for an active and mobile way of life (Omelchenko & Bozhenko-Kurilo, 2023).

In the United Kingdom, university students are experiencing poor well-being and health difficulties (Thorley, 2017). This process has also harmed students who are continuing their university education and have had different problems such as depression, stress, anxiety, fear, and school burnout (Copeland et al., 2021). On the other hand, the coronavirus illness 2019 (COVID-19) epidemic in the Philippines has put Filipino mental health and well-being at risk. While exposed to these harms, there is still a lack of cohesive and comprehensive solutions for combating the degradation of Filipino health (Malolos et al., 2021). Considering the result of the study of Manuela (2023) reveals that Luzon college students need more healthy habits such as rest, exercise, nutrition, water, and temperance.

Particularly, teachers play an essential role in promoting the health and well-being of all young people by making their schools safe and supportive places where learning can happen. Equally, teachers must feel at ease and confident while advocating for and teaching about health. Specific, focused interventions, delivered across the entire school, address the needs of the minority of students who require exceptional support (Tomé et al., 2021). In private tertiary schools in the Cotabato Province in Mindanao, teachers should work to promote professional growth, engage with students, and employ right and efficient teaching practices for online physical education and health courses. Due to the dynamic nature of physical education (PE), lesson planning and delivery must be careful to promote health and well-being and conduct various learning objectives (Estevan et al., 2021).

Since life in Assumption College of Nabunturan and Davao de Oro State College Main Campus is in a transitional stage when college students stay home because of the covid 19 pandemic and become independent health some factors such as having a tight schedule, skipping meals, using fast foods, dieting, as well as the type and amount of physical activity. On the other side, the researcher has not come across a study investigation on the relationship between healthy lifestyle and self-efficacy of physical educators to students' well-being, thus, setting up the research gap of the study. Considering the importance of this issue, the researcher wanted to conduct a study exploring the said variables. This study will serve as a tool for developing proper courses and programs by examining the content, method, pedagogy, and psychology of how lifestyle and physical education teachers contribute to students' well-being enhancement

The main goal of this study is to determine which domain in a healthy lifestyle and physical educators' self-efficacy significantly predicts well-being among college students.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study will sought answers to the following goals:

1. To describe the level of healthy lifestyle among college students in terms of:
 - 1.1. health responsibility;
 - 1.2. physical activity;
 - 1.3. nutrition;
 - 1.4. positive life and perspective;
 - 1.5. interpersonal relations;
 - 1.6. stress management and
 - 1.7. spiritual health.
2. To describe the level of physical educators' self-efficacy assessment of the college students in terms of:
 - 2.1. efficacy for instructional strategies;
 - 2.2. efficacy for classroom management and
 - 2.3. efficacy for student engagement.
3. To describe the level of student well-being among college students in terms of:
 - 3.1. stressors
 - 3.2. social support and
 - 3.3. cognitive problems.
4. Is there a significant relationship between healthy lifestyle and student well-being: and physical educators' self-efficacy and student well-being?
5. To figure out which domain in healthy lifestyle predicts student well-being among college students.
6. To figure out which domain in physical educators' self-efficacy predicts student well-being among college students.

Literature Review

Healthy Lifestyle and Students' Well-being

Schools are one of the keys to promoting healthy lifestyles among college students. Also, students with low levels of engagement in physical activity will lead to poor well-being (Mingazov et al., 2024a). Moreover, a study by Malhotra (2024) states that promoting a quality healthy lifestyle among college students through a study entails that they have moderate levels in physical, mental, and social well-being domains, as they evaluated the health-related qualities of the college students. Another discovery of Omidvar et al. (2024) revealed that the implementation of health education programs for college students effectively elevates their well-being. Additionally, developing programs to promote good and healthy lifestyles among college students is vital in sustaining the health of future working generations, and enhancing physical and overall well-being (Mingazov et al., 2024b). Thus, it is crucial to highlight and offer programs and interventions to elevate and promote college students' general well-being and healthy lifestyle.

Physical Educators Self- Efficacy and Students' Well-being

Be improved via the implementation of various physical fitness activities and a positive exercise attitude. This suggests that physical educators are essential in helping students develop and provide these qualities (Han et al., 2022a). In the same way, a study by Yiming et al. (2024) mentioned that the higher self-efficacy of physical educators has a significant relation to the improvement and development of the overall well-being of college students. Self-efficacy plays a crucial role in setting a good learning environment for college students' well-being, giving the spot to the importance of educators' self-efficacy in enhancing students' well-being in school (Mursandi et al., 2022a). Indeed, physical educators can improve and develop the well-being of college students by fostering passion in teaching physical education thus, it creates a significant influence on self-esteem and well-being based on the studies conducted (Wu & Tien-Liu, 2020). Therefore, physical educators must retain and keep their self-efficacy in terms of excellence and competence in teaching and influencing the total well-being of college students.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive correlation method is appropriate for use in situations where the objective is to research the factors that contribute to a certain phenomenon by depicting the situation at the time of the study when the investigation is being conducted. Establishing correlations between two or more variables within the same population and quantifying the statistical link between them is the focus of correlational research. This type of research does not rely on minor variables to be controlled using statistical methods. The correlational study is differentiated by the fact that just two variables are examined; not even one of them is altered. This is true regardless of whether the variables being measured are categorical or quantitative (Gravetter et al., 2020a).

Respondents

Out of all tertiary education institutions in Davao de Oro, namely Assumption College of Nabunturan and Davao de Oro State College these two (2) higher educational institutions were chosen to stand for the entire population. The subjects of the study will be the teacher education students who specialize in Secondary Education and Elementary Education enrolled in the year 2023-2024 taking physical education subjects. This study applied the cluster sampling technique in selecting the study's respondents. This cluster or area sampling

technique has samples based on individuals rather than clusters, regions, or clusters of subjects that naturally come together (Taherdoost, 2016). Moreover, teacher education students and not under the said program and who are not enrolled in the physical education subjects are excluded as part of the sample of this study. The respondents can withdraw anytime if the study's conduct threatens them. The researcher used the Slovin's formula where "n" pertains to the sample size, "N" refers to population size, and "e" denotes the margin of error to figure out the number of samples.

The researcher gathered the names of the college students from the records of the School Registrar and the program that they belong to. The Registrar's Office provides the total number of college students. Out of 161 teacher education students there will be 114 respondents from Assumption College of Nabunturan and from the total population of 385 teacher education students from Davao de Oro State College 193 were extracted. The respondents included in the study, about 307, based on the Slovin formula computation. Students at the school where the study is done are allowed to take part without facing any punishments, penalties, or loss of benefits. Then, participants' rights to contribute to all knowledge will be carefully considered and agreed upon. Confidentiality and privacy of respondents' information may be bid on in a private study with the utmost discretion. A method of informed permission will also be examined. The research findings are particularly pertinent to the private and state tertiary education institutions in Davao de Oro. The scope and sample size constraints the findings' generalizability. As a result, while there may be shared characteristics, the conclusions may have broad applicability to diverse designs.

Instrument

The researcher adopted an existing questionnaire to the study's context for the independent and dependent variables. The data gathered from the discourse and literature confirmed by a panel of internal and external validators to aid in the questionnaire's design. The respondents completed a questionnaire that includes a demographic profile of college students and three sets of questionnaires for the independent and dependent variables. The first set of the questionnaire dealt with a healthy lifestyle that the college students with the indicators content health responsibility, interpersonal relationship, spiritual health, positive life and perspective, stress management, physical activity, and nutrition. The instrument used in this study was adopted and changed from the standard Adolescent Lifestyle Profile-Revised 2 (ALPR-2) of Gaete et al., (2021) entitled "Adolescent Lifestyle Profile-Revised 2: validity and reliability among adolescents in Chile.

The original questionnaire was changed to contextualize the school setting. The actual items will be simplified or paraphrased to gain a better understanding from the respondents. A panel of experts were confirmed the content. The validity and reliability were assessed at Davao de Oro State College Montevista Branch, answered by college teacher education students to ensure the quality of the tool used by the study. The Cronbach's α was 0.926 which entails an internal consistency of very good. For each item, the respondents are requested to rate the level of a healthy lifestyle using the five-point Likert Scale anchored at (5) Always (4) Often (3) Sometimes (2) Seldom (1) Never.

The instrument's second set is initiated with physical educators' self-efficacy assessed among teacher education college students. It includes three indicators: student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. The research instrument for this variable adopted from a 24-item Ohio State Teacher Efficacy Scale (OSTES) developed by Megan Tschannen-Morana and Anita Woolfolk Hoy (2001) entitled "Teacher efficacy: capturing an elusive construct."

The adopted questionnaire was modified and simplified to fit the study perfectly. A panel of experts validated it. Testing of reliability and validity was conducted at Davao de Oro State College Montevista Branch college teacher education students, Montevista province of Davao de Oro. The Cronbach's α was 0.928 which entails an internal consistency of very good. For each item, the respondents are pleased to ask to rate the level of physical educators' self-efficacy using the five-point Likert Scale anchored at (5) Always (4) Often (3) Sometimes (2) Seldom (1) Never.

The third set of the instruments embarks on student well-being among college students. It will be composed of three indicators: stressors, social support, and cognitive problems. The tool was used in this study was adopted and modified questionnaire from the study of Williams, Pendlebury, Thomas, and Smith (2017) entitled "The Student Well-Being Process Questionnaire (Student WPQ)." Again, the original questionnaire was modified to suit the context of the study further. The panel of experts validated the content. It will also undergo the test of reliability and validity conducted by teacher education students at Davao de Oro State College Montevista Branch. The Cronbach's α was 0.807 which entails an internal consistency of very good. For each item, the respondents were asked to rate the level of well-being of students using the five-point Likert Scale anchored at (5) Always (4) Often (3) Sometimes (2) Seldom (1) Never.

Remarkably, the instrument used was validated by the panel of experts before the conduct of data gathering.

Procedure

This study is a quantitative approach that does not include any experiments. It makes use of the causal effect to characterize any existing link between two variables that have been specified, as well as to determine the direction and amplitude of that association. The descriptive correlation method is appropriate for use in situations where the objective is to research the factors that contribute to a certain phenomenon by depicting the situation at the time of the study when the investigation is being conducted. Establishing

correlations between two or more variables within the same population and quantifying the statistical link between them is the focus of correlational research. This type of research does not rely on minor variables to be controlled using statistical methods. The correlational study is differentiated by the fact that just two variables are examined; not even one of them is altered. This is true regardless of whether the variables being measured are categorical or quantitative (Gravetter et al., 2020b).

The regression analysis technique was used in this research since it was useful in determining the strength of the relationship between the two independent variables and a dependent variable. In addition, regression is a statistical technique that is employed to forecast continuous variables using multiple input variables (Sarstedt & Mooi, 2014). The process entails developing a mathematical relationship between the independent variables and the output, with an estimation of error provided by an optimization algorithm. The quantitative method was appropriate for gathering the data for the target respondents to answer the questions reflected in the survey questionnaire.

This descriptive survey will focus on quantitative data about the problem mentioned above. The quantitative part entails developing an adequate schedule for data collection that allows target respondents to reply to the questions. The data collection strategy was based on the usage of questionnaires. This study aims to find the level of a healthy lifestyle, physical educator self-efficacy, and student well-being among college students. Following approval by the panel member, the data collection for this study will follow the following phases and processes. Internal and external validators will validate the researcher's questionnaire. The researcher will then request authorization by letter approval from the school's administrator to perform the study. The letter of acceptance requested that the researcher function as the study's manager of the survey forms distributed to the study's participants. Similarly, the researcher will get permission from school administrators before distributing survey questionnaires to college students. Additionally, the researcher will write a second letter of authorization to address college students. The researcher delivered the questionnaire individually and will explain the study instrument and its aim.

Additionally, the researcher collected the survey questionnaire following the completion of all items by respondents. Finally, the data will be collated, evaluated, and interpreted in the strictest confidence possible. All data is collected and endorsed for computation, tabulation, and analysis by the statistician. The researcher will surely appreciate the respondents' assistance and trust in getting all necessary data. The researcher explains to the participants that the data gathered from them will be treated with maximum. Thus, to ensure anonymity and confidentiality, will be assigned with individual pseudonyms as a safeguard to their identities. Data will be stored safely to computer for about one to three months during the conduct of the study. Back-up files were also provided to ensure the copies would be safe, the researcher will use a Flash Drive and after this study the data will be destroyed or deleted to assure the participants that the data obtained from them would be strictly for study use only.

The following statistical methods were used for this study to process the responses to the questions at the 0.05 level of significance. The answers to the questionnaire items will be collated and analyzed following their nature. For data analysis and interpretation, this study used the following statistical tools: Mean. It will figure out the level of a healthy lifestyle, physical educators' self-efficacy, and student well-being among college students. Person-r. This statistical treatment will figure out the significance of the relationship between a healthy lifestyle, physical educators' self-efficacy, and student well-being among college students. Linear Regression Analysis. This statistical will figure out if health lifestyle and physical educators' self-efficacy predict students' well-being among college students.

Ethical Considerations

The University of Mindanao Ethics Reviewer Committee (UMERC) granted ethical approval for this study under UMERC Protocol No. UMERC-2023-417. An official document verifying compliance, issued by the UMERC, was necessary before the commencement of data collecting. Participants will be required to provide informed and written consent. All information provided will be carefully examined, analyzed to prevent any instances of plagiarism or fabrication, and treated as highly confidential. Participating institutions will only share the results as a group, rather than individually.

There are considerable ethical issues and concerns that have specific ramifications for this quantitative inquest. Such issues and concerns may arise primarily from the methodology involved in this study. The ethical contests that are pertinent to this research concern issues of the right to conduct the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. In conducting this study full ethical standards were followed following the study etiquette evaluations as well as the consistency measures, specifically in dealing the participants along with their information enumerated as, but not restricted to:

Voluntary participations. The participants from the chosen institution were given their own- willpower to be involved in the study with no type of result or punishment or loss of advantages. Thusly, after the reason and the advantages of the examination was portrayed at the same time introduced to the contributing school. At that point, the privileges of the respondents to contribute to the collection of information were painstakingly considered and followed upon.

Privacy and confidentiality. The researcher secured the privacy as well as with most extreme secrecy the participants' individual data that might be essential to the research. Informed consent process. The study survey inquiry form was liberated from specialized terms that make it simpler for the participants to comprehend. It provides the participants a vivid understanding of the advantages they might acquire once the conduction of this research is finished. The assent form and informed consent was given to the participants for them

to answer upon the approval of the school head.

Recruitment. The distribution of the participants indicated how the participants were dispersed. Besides, the information assortment systems were demonstrated, just as how the interview guide form was distributed to the participants, and the way of participants engaged with the investigation.

Risks. The study did not involve in high risks of situations that the respondents may experience in physical, psychological, or socio-economic concerns.

Benefits. The result of the study benefits the institutions involved, students and other educational sectors.

Plagiarism. The research has no indication or proof of somebody effort as his own. The research had gone through plagiarism detector like Grammarly or Turnitin software.

Falsification. The research has no hint of intentionally confusing the work to suit a method or hypothetical anticipation as well as it was found out to have no proof of over asserting or distortion.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The research has no hint of irreconcilable circumstance like the divulgence of COI which is a lot of conditions where proficient judgment concerning essential concern, for example, members' benefit or the legitimacy of the exploration will in general be affected by an optional concern, for example money related or scholarly gains or acknowledgments.

Deceit. The research has no hint of deceiving the participants of the study to any mischief.

Authorship. The author of the research is a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health at University of Southeastern Philippines. The author of the research experienced arrangement of paper amendments in view of the proposals made by his research adviser which is a graduate of Doctor of Philosophy in Education major in Physical Education. The study likewise adhered to the measures of the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee and the Assumption College of Nabunturan Ethics Review Board for the rules of moral thought. After their endorsement, the research had to undergo preliminary testing and comply with the Research Ethics Certificate. At the same time, the information gathered will be deciphered for the consistency of the research inquiry.

Results and Discussion

This section provides a deconstruction of the data collected from the responses of the respondents in the study regarding the healthy lifestyle and self-efficacy of physical educators as a predictor of students' well-being. The presentation was organized according to the following: Initially, the level of student's healthy lifestyle, self-efficacy of physical educators and the levels of students' well-being. Secondly, the discussion will focus on the significance of the study's findings regarding the relationship between healthy lifestyle and students' well-being and self-efficacy of physical educators and students' well-being and the regression analysis of pertinent variables.

Table 1. Respondents' Level of Healthy Lifestyle

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Health Responsibility	2.89	0.73	Moderate
Physical Activity	3.23	0.73	Moderate
Nutrition	3.29	0.62	Moderate
Positive Life Perspective	4.19	0.87	High
Interpersonal Relations	4.08	0.71	High
Stress Management	3.56	0.69	High
Spiritual Health	3.75	0.57	High
Overall	3.57	0.52	High

Table 1 displays the ratings of the students' healthy lifestyle, with an average rating of 3.57, which is considered high. The standard deviation is 0.52. The respondents' high scores in indicated elements, such as positive life perspective, interpersonal interactions, stress management, and spiritual health, were attributed to a significant degree. However, health responsibility, physical activity, and nutrition are described to a moderate level of degree. The result implies that most college students practice a healthy lifestyle while continuing their academic life. The mean scores, determined based on the highest to lowest indicators, are as follows: The ratings for positive life perspective, interpersonal relations, spiritual health, stress management, nutrition, physical activity, and health responsibility are as follows: 4.19 or high for positive life perspective with the standard deviation of 0.87, 4.08 or high with a standard deviation of 0.71 for interpersonal relations, 3.75 or higher for spiritual health with the standard deviation of 0.57, 3.56 or high for stress management with 0.69 standard deviation, 3.29 or moderate for nutrition with a standard deviation of 0.62, 3.23 or moderate for physical activity with 0.73 as standard deviation, and 2.89 or moderate with a standard deviation of 0.73 for health responsibility.

The indicator with the highest mean among all the indicators is that college students who maintain a positive life perspective are more likely to maintain a healthful lifestyle. It was discovered that college students exhibited a higher level of self-esteem and a more optimistic outlook on the future when it came to setting objectives. It was mentioned that they experience a sense of self-assurance when they accomplish something positive. College students exhibit a greater degree of intrinsic motivation, which results in a sincere

interest in personal development and learning, rather than external rewards. Additionally, it was discovered that college students are more actively involved in their academic pursuits, participating in class activities, and seeking out additional learning opportunities.

The study suggests that college students have strong interpersonal relationships with their peers, teachers, family, and other social networks, indicating a healthy lifestyle. The significance of a college student's social life in fostering general growth and supporting a healthy lifestyle is evident in this expression. College students are also surrounded by supportive peers and family members, which creates an environment of belonging and security. College students have expressed their satisfaction in assisting and supporting others. They are conscientious about empathizing with others' emotions and resolving issues through dialogue rather than engaging in physical confrontation. Cultivating robust interpersonal ties during undergraduate studies can result in enduring friendships and valuable professional networks.

College students often exhibit prominent level of spiritual health based on the results of the study, demonstrating a strong belief in their spirituality and a clear sense of purpose, and meaning in life. College students allocate a significant amount of their resources towards engaging in prayer and meditation, as they passionately believe in the efficacy of these practices in providing guidance and support in overcoming the various problems and uncertainties that arise during their college years. Additionally, it was disclosed that college students partake in various religious endeavors to enhance their spiritual health and fortify their beliefs per their faiths. College students are more motivated to pursue their education with a profound and unwavering sense of purpose and dedication.

Another notable determinant of a healthy lifestyle is stress management; in this study, a phenomenon that is particularly prevalent among college students. The findings indicate that college students manage tasks that cause them to experience stress. College students are demonstrating a sense of acknowledging the realities of life and prioritizing activities that bring them happiness despite experiencing only modest levels of sleep and rest due to the demands of college life. College students are willing to confide in their close peers or family members, seeking guidance and solutions for their life problems. This suggests that college students exhibit proficient and efficient strategies and talents in effectively managing pressures, resulting in noteworthy and meaningful academic, social, and personal outcomes.

Nutrition is moderately noted among college students and is considered one of the indicators of a healthy lifestyle. This suggests that college students with a modest level of nutrition in their diet have balanced but not optimal eating habits. One of the contributing elements to this is the availability and cost of food. These effects can have diverse consequences on their physical health, cognitive abilities, and entire state of being. College students with suboptimal nutrition levels may still need to improve in crucial vitamins and minerals. While moderate nutrition can contribute to a satisfactory quality of life, students may still need to fully experience the advantages of a highly nutritious diet, which include enhanced physical fitness, mental well-being, and overall life contentment.

College students engage in physical activity to a moderate extent. Respondents said that college students exhibit a modest level of engagement in various forms of physical activity and active leisure activities with their family members and colleagues despite their academic schedule and other demands. Furthermore, it was found out that, college students prefer engaging in walking or other active activities during their free time. College students engage in moderate physical activity may participate in certain physical activities but may need to meet the required levels for optimal health benefits. Their total lifestyle is affected by this amount of activity in multiple ways.

Lastly, health responsibility is evident in the healthy lifestyle of college students, serving as a sign of the moderate mean score. The results indicate that college students have a reasonable level of health responsibility. It was shown that college students rarely visit their doctors when sick. Additionally, it has been found that college students have a moderate level of involvement in attending health programs and reading articles on health topics. They also have a moderate level of engagement in seeking guidance from their school counselor when needed. Nevertheless, college students refrain from engaging in risky behaviors and activities that could harm their health, as the study's findings indicate.

The prominent level of healthy lifestyle responses among college students suggests that a healthy lifestyle was much observed among college students. Specifically, the students reported high positive life perspectives, interpersonal relations, spiritual health, and stress management. However, college students need help with a healthy lifestyle. Specifically, students reported moderate nutrition levels in their eating habits, engagement in physical activity, and health responsibility. This result confirms the statements of Pérez (2022) that promoting a healthy lifestyle is essential in college life, as it helps alleviate physical, mental, and social components to achieve well-balanced health and functionality. Moreover, college students know the maintenance of a healthy lifestyle, which encompasses adopting the proper dietary habits, taking part in regular physical activity, organizing their sleep patterns, and managing drug intake, all of which contribute to their overall well-being (Del & Villavicencio et al., 2023).

A study by Rafat and Mona (2021) entails that students' spiritual well-being has a detrimental impact on their ability to lead healthy lifestyles. Other findings of Tomy and Naaz (2019) reveal that overcoming obstacles to encourage a healthy lifestyle among college students, such as addressing the impact of diet and stress on overall well-being. It is crucial to consider these obstacles when striving to enhance the general well-being of college students. Additionally, a positive perspective promotes good lifestyle behaviors through behavior change and direct physiological advantages, improving overall health (Lianoy, 2023).

On the other hand, Mahensa et al. (2022) claim that spirituality and family cohesion influence various elements of a healthy lifestyle

among students, fostering spiritual growth, interpersonal ties, health responsibility, physical exercise, and stress management. However, college students show suboptimal health behaviors concerning sunshine exposure, hydration, air quality, rest, physical activity, and nutrition. There is a requirement to promote and provide guidance in health education and promotion (Rusally et al., 2021). Furthermore, Mohamed et al. (2020) also mentioned that the prevalence of an unhealthy lifestyle among college students, characterized by inadequate nutrition and a lack of participation in physical activities, has been associated with health complications and academic underperformance. Thus, by encouraging healthy behaviors and persistently pushing for and implementing various health education initiatives among college students, we may enhance and foster a healthier environment within educational settings.

Table 2. Level of Self-efficacy of Physical Educators

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Efficacy for Instructional Strategies	3.85	0.82	High
Efficacy for Classroom Management	4.00	0.82	High
Efficacy for Student Engagement	4.14	0.84	High
Overall	4.00	0.76	High

Table 2 displays the scores of the variable self-efficacy of physical educators. The total mean is 4.00, indicating a high level. The standard deviation is 0.76. The responders demonstrated a high level of self-efficacy in various areas related to physical education, including instructional effectiveness, classroom management, and student involvement. The mean scores, obtained by ranking the indicators from highest to lowest, resulted in the following total mean score: 4.14, indicating a high level of efficacy for student engagement with a standard deviation of 0.84; a mean score of 4.00, again indicating a high level of efficacy for classroom management and with a standard deviation of 0.82; and lastly, a mean score of 3.85, again indicating a high level of efficacy for instructional strategies with a numerical data of standard deviation of 0.82.

Among all other indicators, the most frequently observed indicator of self-efficacy in physical educators among college students is efficacy for student engagement, with the highest mean value. In this study, the self-efficacy of physical educators in student engagement is frequently observed, and it implies that college students believe that their physical educators inspire them to participate in school-related activities with the utmost enthusiasm. Another outcome is that physical educators encourage students' creativity and assist them in appreciating their education. Additionally, physical educators strive to foster critical thinking among students by facilitating the development and provision of various engaging and meaningful class activities.

Efficacy in classroom management is another indicator that is characterized as high. In the current study, it was discovered that college students frequently observe and evaluate the self-efficacy of physical educators in organizing their classes. It indicates that the college has observed that physical education educators can ensure that students adhere to class regulations, establish a consistent classroom routine, and offer activities that operate efficiently. The responses also indicate that physical educators can effectively manage disruptive behavior and defiant students during classes to create a more conducive learning environment.

Finally, the efficacy of instructional strategies with a high descriptive level in physical educators is also important. According to the study's results, physical educators' self-efficacy about the instructional strategies observed by college students suggests that they employ differentiated assessments and strategies to accommodate the students' levels and requirements. Additionally, college students' responses indicated that physical educators offer alternative explanations for students experiencing challenges during the lesson and class activities, as well as activities that assess students' understanding of the lesson. This indicates that physical educators' self-efficacy in terms of the efficacy of instructional strategies in their classes is well-recognized and effectively implemented during the delivery of classes. In summary, the research findings suggest that physical educators' self-efficacy is frequently assessed through the observations and assessments of college students regarding their ability to promote and deliver learning experiences in an educational setting effectively.

With these results, Finnegan (2013a) supported the idea that the concept of teacher self-efficacy centers on the philosophy and belief that teachers have in order to bring about the desired changes in student success. It also influences teachers' teaching behaviors and their motivation to teach. A study reveals that teacher self-efficacy is derived from and based on Bandura's Social theory, which refers to instructors' beliefs in their capacity and skills to effectively influence the learning process of students (Martin & Mulvihill, 2019). In addition, as stated by Finnegan (2013b), educators with low self-efficacy are less likely to continue in the face of challenging circumstances. In contrast, those with high self-efficacy are expected to have a positive attitude and dedication when confronting challenging scenarios. An effective teaching style is associated with reduced burnout among teachers. Additionally, the teaching style is given priority in student engagement, leading to a more profound comprehension (Amasha & Assadi, 2024).

Teacher self-efficacy provides an environment for the students to perform at their optimal level. Research reveals that positive classroom climates impact student engagement, self-efficacy, and learning experiences, underscoring the critical role of supportive environments in improving teacher self-efficacy (Khuhro, 2024). Efficacy for instructional strategies is directly connected to a teacher's belief in their ability to teach effectively, known as teacher self-efficacy. These strategies are crucial in influencing classroom dynamics and students' academic outcomes (Bachtiar, 2024). Furthermore, classroom management and student engagement among college students are significantly influenced by teacher self-efficacy. The study conducted by Wang and He (2022) revealed that the efficacy of teaching strategies, classroom management, and student engagement has a positive impact on the self-efficacy of teachers. Other

findings show that physical educators with high self-efficacy in lesson preparation, teaching methods, student engagement in class interactions, devising learning evaluations, and self-evaluation demonstrate strong self-esteem in their teaching abilities (Salles et al., 2020a). Therefore, physical educators' self-efficacy in college teaching is essential for student engagement and development in promoting holistic learning.

Table 3. *Level of Student Well-being*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Stressors	3.18	0.65	Moderate
Social Support	2.29	0.92	Low
Cognitive Problem	3.13	0.94	Moderate
Overall	2.87	0.16	Moderate

Table 3 presents the quantitative data on the well-being scores of students. The overall mean score is 2.87, which is considered moderate. The standard deviation is 0.16. The students' moderate level of well-being can be attributed to the respondents' moderate evaluations in various aspects, particularly stressors and cognitive problems. Nevertheless, the level of social support is said to be low. Based on the responses gained in this study, the numerical data was tabulated, computed, and examined; the mean scores are organized in descending order, resulting in the following mean score based on the statistical analysis: 3.18 or moderate for stressors with a 0.65 as standard deviation, we have 3.13 or moderate for the cognitive problem with the standard deviation of 0.94, and social support with 2.29 or in low degree with a standard deviation of 0.92.

College students exhibit the greatest level of student well-being when they are exposed to stressors. It suggests that the majority of students have moderately observed this phenomenon. Students often struggle to satisfy their own and others' academic expectations, demonstrating that they make significant decisions about their education, future, and career. Another stressor for college students is the abundance of responsibilities. Their academic pursuits may be disrupted by the multitude of tasks they must complete simultaneously. The findings suggest that college students experience moderate dissatisfaction with their academic pursuits, perceive courses as unappealing, and lack a sense of success in their academic pursuits. Furthermore, we moderately monitor the engagement and decisions of college students about intimate relationships and conflicts. They occasionally experience letdowns, disappointment, and trust issues, as well as conflicts with companions.

In addition, cognitive problems are a prominent indication of student well-being among college students, with the second-highest average score. Respondents exhibited positive replies on memory issues in both work and non-work settings over the past two weeks, including instances of misplacing items, decreased attentiveness, difficulties with concentration, and making mistakes. The survey revealed that college students often reported a decrease in productivity during the last two weeks, both in terms of the amount of work accomplished and their ability to perform tasks during outdoor work. Over the past two weeks, college students have encountered difficulties with their memory when studying. This discovery indicates that college students experienced modest cognitive impairments that could result in problems with focus, memory, and problem-solving abilities, which may hinder their academic performance and daily activities.

Finally, social support is the student well-being indicator with the lowest mean. Its primary objective is to assess the extent to which individuals, through their social connections with other individuals and groups, Consequently, the results suggested that college students have good social support and link with different individuals; they have a person or people in their lives who would provide tangible support for them, such as money for tuition and providing for their daily needs. College students also reveal that they experience strong bonds and a sense of belongingness, in which they are comfortable sharing problems about their social life, having a good relationship with parents, and hanging out with their friends. Having someone with constant communication and emotional support can provide a good sense of belonging and buffer against stress and anxiety.

College students demonstrate a moderate degree of well-being. These college students possess the ability to effectively manage and adapt to the difficulties they encounter. Students with a moderate level of well-being succeed in completing their academic endeavors. While they remain involved and passionate, they may encounter difficulties in their performance as a result of nervousness or external pressures. Such a high degree of student well-being enables them to actively engage in extracurricular activities, promoting an intense sense of belonging and community. This category of students is satisfied with their college life experience, but they may delve into distinct aspects of their life that they desire to enhance and refine. It implies that students possess proficient organizational abilities, but they do not consistently apply them. College students often face difficulties managing their academics, social lives, and self-care due to intermittent periods of feeling overwhelmed.

With this finding it was supported by Zhao (2024a) that, emphasizing the importance of student well-being in the context of college students is crucial, given its interconnectedness with their self-concept, mental health, relationships, and holistic development. The development and enhancement of well-being facilitates academic, career, and social assimilation. In addition, students' well-being is critical; it directly impacts their happiness and overall satisfaction with life. The aforementioned findings indicate that factors such as mental health programs in schools, leisure activities, family support, and interpersonal interactions have a substantial impact on student happiness. Examining and assessing the academic stress and obstacles in the setting is crucial for enhancing student well-being. To enhance students' overall development, we should tailor interventions and programs for health and well-being campaigns to their specific needs. Therefore, placing a high priority on student well-being is crucial for creating a positive college experience and

promoting academic achievement (Reddy, 2023). Considering this result of Rajput (2024) that, it is crucial to prioritize the preservation of college students' psychological well-being and overall health by implementing effective stress management techniques. College students face a wide range of stresses, including academic pressures, financial worries, social issues, and uncertainty about their future professions. Unmonitored and unhandled stressors can lead to unhealthy behaviors and negatively impact their mental health.

Another study by Yang and Chen (2023) conducted reveals that, the importance of effectively resolving cognitive problems in college students. This has a favorable effect on their general well-being, academic achievement, and future development. Students' cognitive functioning can be adversely impacted by anxiety and melancholy, resulting in detrimental consequences on their learning process and daily activities. Besides, among college students, maladaptive thinking patterns are a prevalent cognitive issue that is significantly linked to depression and other mental health complications. This can result in severe challenges for students in both their academic and personal lives (Jaffri et al., 2021). Given this point, that the mental well-being of college students is an essential aspect of public health, and cultivating it is necessary for guaranteeing that the next generation will attain a high level of overall well-being and make meaningful contributions to society (Dong & Shen, 2022).

Significant relationship between Healthy Lifestyle and Students Well-Being

The main objective of this study is to investigate the significant connection between the healthy lifestyle of college students and their well-being. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to establish the relationship between the two variables under investigation. The resulting calculations are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. *Significance of the Relationship between Levels of Healthy Lifestyle and Students well-being of College Students*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r-square</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Healthy Lifestyle	Students Well-Being	0.109	0.0119	0.056	Do not Reject H_0

* $p < 0.05$

The results indicate a very weak correlation between a healthy lifestyle and students' well-being, as evidenced by an R-value of 0.109. The correlation observed does not reach statistical significance, as indicated by the p-value of 0.056, which exceeds the predetermined significance level of 0.05. The null hypothesis, which suggests that there is no significant correlation between a healthy lifestyle and the well-being of students, was not able to be disproven. Therefore, the decision to reject the null hypothesis stays unchanged.

The study findings show that there is no significant correlation between college students' healthy lifestyles and their well-being. The correlation between college students' lifestyles and well-being is intricate and multifaceted, with certain lifestyle parameters exhibiting no significant association with students' well-being. This finding aligns with Ravi and Gamal's (2023) study, which found that college students' lifestyle choices do not affect their overall well-being. The study demonstrates a clear correlation between frequent moderate or strenuous physical exercise, skipping breakfast, and maintaining healthy sleep patterns and overall well-being. This study evaluated these and demonstrated their influence on the well-being of college students.

In summary, research suggests that lifestyle behaviors such as engaging in physical activity and maintaining excellent sleep quality significantly impact the overall well-being of college students. The same investigation disclosed that students adhere to healthy behaviors; however, they continue to experience difficulties with the quality of their sleep and diet, which are essential for preserving their overall well-being. Intriguingly, the quality of life tends to decline as academic levels increase, suggesting that academic tension harms well-being and lifestyle (Qiao, 2023). Furthermore, a study indicated that when assessing the lifestyle of college students, factors such as socioeconomic status and happiness level significantly influence their behavior. However, the conformity to healthy lifestyle habits was still low. This phenomenon is especially noticeable in the fields of diet and fitness (Dungog et al., 2021). These findings suggest that although lifestyle aspects are essential, they may only sometimes directly impact the well-being of college students. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt a more comprehensive approach to health campaigns and promotion that considers mental, social, and economic elements.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy of Physical Educators and Student Well-Being*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r-square</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Self-Efficacy of Physical Educators	Students Well-being	0.196*	0.0384	0.001	Reject H_0

* $p < 0.05$

The results suggest a significant correlation between physical educators' self-efficacy and college students' well-being. A statistical analysis's R-value of 0.196 supports this. The correlation between these variables is statistically significant, as indicated by a p-value of 0.001 below the predetermined significance level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, which posits no significant correlation between physical educators' self-efficacy and college students' well-being.

The current study reveals a significant correlation between physical educators' self-efficacy and college students, well-being. The data clearly shows that self-efficacy among physical educators impacts the well-being of college students. Thus, physical education (PE) educators serve a vital role in shaping the well-being of college students. This finding is consistent with the study of Li and Huang (2024) state that the well-being of college students is influenced by their involvement in sports and physical activity, with social development playing a crucial role in this connection. Additionally, physical education classes conducted through recreational activities

encourage participation in physical activity and boost cognitive and emotional motivation, fostering student connection and enhancing overall satisfaction and involvement in PE courses (Aquino, 2023a). As they establish students' well-being and life satisfaction, enjoyment and active participation are essential (Sian et al., 2023).

In addition, the findings of Aquino (2023b) reveal that cultivating a loving and dynamic physical education (PE) environment establishes crucial connections for PE educators in promoting the well-being of children. Creating a setting encouraging active participation and enjoyment may improve emotional and psychological health. Therefore, physical education educators play a crucial role in fostering a comprehensive education that enhances college students' cognitive and emotional well-being. They answer the demand for organized programs prioritizing physical and psychological advancement.

Table 6. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Healthy Lifestyle and Self-Efficacy of Physical Educators to Students Well-Being

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(Constant)	2.384	0.244				
Health Lifestyle	-0.29	0.087	-0.025	-0.342	0.733	Do not Reject Ho
Self-Efficacy of Physical Educators	0.172	0.059	0.212*	2.912	0.004	Reject Ho

Dependent Variable: Students Well-Being
 R= 0.197* R2= 0.039
 F ratio= 6.120 p-value= 0.002
 *p<0.05

The information provided in Table 6 comprises regression coefficients utilized to evaluate the significance of overall healthy lifestyle and physical educator self-efficacy. The Multiple Regression Analysis produced an F-value of 6.12, associated with a matching value of 0.002. The findings suggest no significant influence of a healthy lifestyle on students' well-being since the probability value exceeds 0.05. However, the second independent variable in regression analysis shows that physical educators' self-efficacy impacts students' well-being, as indicated by a probability value of less than 0.05. The coefficient of determination (R2) of 0.039 indicates that the self-efficacy of physical educators can suggest 3.9% of the variability in college students' well-being. Other factors influence the other 96.1%. To summarize, the variable healthy lifestyle does not impact the well-being of students. In contrast, the second variable influences the well-being of college students, as determined by the statistical analysis conducted in this study.

The regression analysis of this study, as shown in Table 6, indicates that a healthy lifestyle does not significantly affect the well-being of college students. The self-efficacy of physical educators, as the second independent variable, directly impacts the well-being of college students. These results were consistent with the discoveries of Oliynyk et al. (2020) states that, although college students possess ample knowledge regarding healthy lifestyle habits, a significant proportion of them exhibit suboptimal physical health levels, morpho-functional impairments, and chronic disorders.

Hence, promoting a wholesome way of life is crucial for augmenting students' academic achievements and overall well-being. Research on lifestyle characteristics among college students has yielded varied results.

Another study by Han et al. (2022b) also mentioned that physical educators promote students' engagement in physical activity, and improved physical fitness can have a good effect on the general well-being of college students by enhancing their self-confidence. Employing distinct ways to boost positive exercise behaviors and improve physical fitness reliably augments college students' mental health and well-being. Additionally, a study conducted in Bandar Lampung confirmed an educational environment's crucial role in enhancing college students' self-efficacy and well-being. The study suggests that a pleasant educational environment, led by competent and efficient physical education instructors, is crucial for enhancing college students' quality of life and general well-being (Mursandi et al., 2022b). Finally, proficient physical educators substantially impact physical fitness and healthy habits, which strongly correlates with students' self-confidence, influencing their mental health and general well-being (Han et al., 2022c).

Table 7. Regression Analysis on the Domains of Self-Efficacy of Physical Educators as Predictors to Students Well-Being

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE (B)				
(Constant)	2.225	0.186				
Efficacy for Instructional Strategies	-0.004	0.070	-0.006	-0.006	0.949	Do not Reject Ho
Efficacy for Classroom Management	0.096	0.074	0.128	1.293	0.197	Do not Reject Ho
Efficacy for Student Engagement	0.006	0.069	0.090	0.951	0.342	Do not Reject Ho

Dependent Variable: Students Well-being
 R= 0.202* R2= 0.041
 F-ratio= 4.285 p-value= 0.006
 *p<0.05

The statistical data provided in Table 7 comprises regression coefficients that are utilized to analyze and measure the substantial impact of physical educators' general self-efficacy on the well-being of college students. The Multiple Regression Analysis resulted in an F-value of 4.285, statistically significant with a p-value of 0.006. The findings suggest that the self-efficacy of physical educators has a considerable impact on the well-being of college students, as indicated by a probability value of less than 0.005. The R² value of 0.041 indicates that the self-efficacy of physical educators can explain 4.1% of the variability in college students' well-being, while other factors influence the other 95.9%.

When examining the individual indicators of self-efficacy of physical educators, it was found that three of them do not have a significant influence on well-being among college students. However, self-efficacy has a considerable effect when considering the combined indicators of efficacy for instructional strategies, efficacy for classroom management, and efficacy for student engagement. It emphasizes the importance of viewing self-efficacy of physical educators holistically rather than focusing solely on individual aspects when aiming to impact college students' well-being. Upon analyzing the specific self-efficacy indicators among physical educators, the statistical result revealed that three have no significant effect on the well-being of college students. Nevertheless, self-efficacy has a significant impact when the combined self-efficacy of physical educators' indicators for instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement is considered. These findings highlight the significance of taking a comprehensive approach to assessing the self-efficacy and effectiveness of physical educators rather than just considering certain factors to influence the well-being of college students positively.

Table 7 indicates that the efficacy of instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement does not directly influence or impact indicators of the well-being of college students. The regression coefficient was employed to investigate the significant influence of the overall self-efficacy of physical educators on the well-being of college students. The results of the Simple Linear Regression analysis indicated that the well-being of college students significantly impacts the overall self-efficacy of physical educators when considering the indicators as a whole. The result implies that physical educators' overall effectiveness and competence in schools among college students and other factors may also be crucial in shaping and improving student well-being outcomes. The overall self-efficacy of physical educators was found to predict college students' well-being even though the null hypothesis is not rejected.

As previously discussed in the study, the outcome of the analysis aligns with the theories discussed. Specifically, a study by Salles et al. (2020b) stated that physical education educators possess a high level of self-efficacy, and there are strong correlations between many components of teaching self-efficacy, emphasizing its significant influence on instructors' conduct and student involvement. However, some studies also mentioned that teachers with a lower level of self-efficacy led to reduced student engagement and participation in activities, potentially negatively affecting students' overall well-being (Shu, 2022). Moreover, the lack of self-efficacy and confidence in their abilities among instructors and students results in a passive attitude among college students, which has a detrimental impact on their engagement and academic achievement (Teane & Gombwe, 2022). Therefore, this illustrates how teachers' self-efficacy in their abilities is crucial in creating and fostering a positive and supportive atmosphere that results in better student achievements. It emphasizes the need for educators to support the development and maintenance of high self-confidence to enhance student involvement and well-being.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are presented in this section as a consequence of the study's findings. The overall mean of college students' healthy lifestyles is high, with a high life perspective, interpersonal relations, spiritual health, stress management, moderate nutrition, physical activity, and health responsibility. It implies that college students maintain a healthful lifestyle. Conversely, physical educators' self-efficacy is found to be high in student engagement, classroom administration, and instructional strategies, with an overall mean that suggests a high level of self-efficacy among physical educators. It suggests that the self-efficacy of physical educators is frequently observed in the execution of activities in the classroom. The study indicates that college students have a moderate level of well-being, with moderate stressors, moderate cognitive problems, and moderate social support. The aggregate meaning of the data suggests that college students have a moderate level of well-being. It demonstrates that college students are moderately attentive to all aspects of their well-being.

The study also indicates no significant relationship between healthy lifestyle among college students and their well-being. The combined indicators of healthy lifestyle do not significantly influence students' well-being. Therefore, while college students' healthy lifestyle may not be the sole determining factor in their ability to practice and manage their well-being, it can still indirectly impact their life satisfaction. However, the appropriate programs, support and accommodation for college students can sustain and maintain healthy living and overcome health challenges and may continue to improve an overall health. On the other hand, there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy of physical educators' self-efficacy and students' well-being among college students. The combined indicators of physical educators' self-efficacy significantly influence the well-being of college students. These findings align with Zhao study (2024b), which entails that the broad spectrum of well-being encompasses various aspects such as self-perception, mental health, and interpersonal connections. These aspects are greatly influenced by the quality of education and social engagement facilitated by instructors. Physical education teachers with a greater level of self-efficacy can positively influence students' emotional regulation, stress management, and social competence. This has a significant effect on the overall development and well-being of students.

Multiple research studies have established a correlation between college students' healthy lifestyle choices and their impact on their overall well-being. The outcome suggests that the way of life significantly affects the well-being of college students. The study indicated that many college students exhibit detrimental behaviors, including inadequate dietary choices, insufficient participation in physical exercise, suboptimal sleep patterns, and missing routine medical examinations. These factors contribute to health problems that undermine one's well-being. In addition, according to the research results, it is evident that upholding a nutritious way of life significantly influences the overall wellbeing of university students. Therefore, in order to enhance and improve the overall quality of life of college students, universities need to establish methods and programs that emphasize the need of encouraging college students to adopt healthier lifestyles (Al-Amari, 2015).

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are offered: Firstly, school administrators, heads, and teachers are advised to continue monitoring, checking, and providing programs that address health concerns based on the needs of the students, such as stress and mental and other health-related concerns. Despite this, most indicators of a healthy lifestyle show moderate to high descriptive levels. On the other hand, data interpretation suggests no significant relationship between a healthy lifestyle and well-being among college students. It is still essential to continue schools' programs and interventions to maintain a healthy lifestyle for students. Students also should participate actively and collaboratively with their family members or guardians to implement effective programs and continue to practice healthy behaviors for a holistic development of students' well-being, even though all indicators of students' well-being gained moderate descriptive levels. Secondly, physical educators in college institutions are still recommended to attend training and workshop seminars to upgrade and improve more and constantly maintain their excellence in teaching based on the new demands of the generations and the contemporary setting in delivering meaningful and fun fitness and healthy activities in inspiring students to become more health-conscious despite of all indicators from self-efficacy of physical educators gained high descriptive score levels and significantly influenced student well-being of college students. In addition, they monitor the impact of interventions and program implementation, conduct continuous assessments, and collect feedback from students to help identify other areas for improvement and provide valuable insights for physical educators. Furthermore, conducting longitudinal studies can offer deeper insight into exploring college students' health practices, lifestyle, and well-being; longitudinal data can help track progress, monitor, and identify patterns over an extended period. In the future, researchers should explore other dimensions or qualitative studies on themes related to healthy lifestyles and physical educators' self-efficacy.

The research will enrich the analysis of how these factors impact students' well-being among college students. Finally, sharing the study's findings with other educators and policy makers is essential. The insights gained from this investigation can contribute to evidence-based practices and educational policies that promote healthy lifestyles and self-efficacy for teachers' and students' well-being, leading to improved student outcomes.

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